

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MBAVINA ONGUENE****FIRST NAME: ANTOINE****PROGRAM CODE: DRCTh****COURSE COD: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: CLEENEWERCK**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What are the different parts of an essay writing?

- Researching – writing – oral examination.
- Researching -draft - conclusion.
- Introduction – development - conclusion.** ¹
- Reading – footnote - bibliography.

2. We say there is plagiarism.

- When the writer uses the citation of an author.
- When the writer uses a source information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.** ²

¹ EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*, <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf>, (accessed September 18, 2019), 4.

²EUCLID 2015, 9.

- When the writer uses the name of an author.
 - When the writer formulates the title of his dissertation.
3. **The actual writing of a thesis is.**
- The completing writing of the Major Paper.
 - The completing writing of the introduction and the conclusion.
 - The writing of the abstract.
 - The chapter-by-chapter roadmap for completing the work.**³
4. **The title is an important factor in sharing research because**
- It wrote in the first page.
 - It identifies the content of your study and the retrieval purposes.**⁴
 - It is written at the end of the writing.
 - The author is the best writer.
5. **There are two usual ways of quoting a text.**
- The parenthetical citation and the in-text citation.
 - The notes style and the sources consulted online.
 - The notes-bibliography style and the author-date style.**⁵

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 29.

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe 2008, 166.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 142.

- The access data and the commercial databases.
6. **The parenthetical citations include enough information for readers to find the full citation in your reference list. There are:**
- The name of the author, the edition, and the date of publication.
- The name of the author, the date of publication, and the page number.**⁶
- The name of the author, the title of the book, and the page number.
- The name of the author, the place of publication, and the page number.
7. **We use software of Zotero for a few reasons.**
- The teacher asks to use it.
- To insert footnotes and to indicate the reference list.**⁷
- To save time during writing.
- To correct spelling of words while writing.
8. **A good introduction to a doctoral thesis contains four points:**
- Reading, note taking, redaction and proofreading
- Time, knowledge, spelling, and writing.
- Title, problem, summary, and writing.

⁶ Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 222.

⁷ Google. *ACA-401D: International academic writing (doctorate)*. EUCLID. Last modified 2015. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-2/>, (accessed October 20, 2019), 93.

Context, problem, purpose, and research questions.⁸

9. There are also two ways to cite a text:

The spelling and the references.

The in-text citation and the list of works cited.⁹

The bibliography and the list of works cited.

The author-date style and the parenthetical citation

10. **There are two ways to present the references of the cited publications**

The in-text citations and the author-date style.

The notes style and the reference list.

The author-date style and notes-bibliography style.¹⁰

The reference list and the spelling.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 33-34.

⁹ EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*, Last modified 2015. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/CUEsEiHd7B/ACA-401%20Coursepack.pdf> (accessed September 18, 2019), 15.

¹⁰ Google. Turabian Style: In-Text (Parenthetical) Citations & Reference List. Bennett College. Last modified July 20, 2011. <http://libraryguides.bennett.edu/home/writing/chicago-turabian-style/turabian-style-in-text-parenthetical-citations--reference-list> (accessed October 30, 2019).

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Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.